

SHORT FORM OF THE QUIET QUITTING SCALE: A TURKISH ADAPTATION STUDY OF VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

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ABSTRACT:

This study aims to adapt the Quiet Quitting Scale developed by Talukder and Prieto (2025) into Turkish and to examine evidence of validity and reliability for its short form. The sample comprised 413 administrative personnel employed at Süleyman Demirel University and reached via convenience sampling; after 23 participants who marked the attention-check item and two multivariate outliers were excluded, analyses were conducted with 388 participants. The dataset was randomly divided into two subsamples for exploratory factor analysis and confirmatory factor analysis. Exploratory factor analysis indicated that items with weak representation in the original scale should be removed, yielding a unidimensional 5-item short form consisting of SI4, SI6, SI7, SI8, and SI9, with factor loadings ranging from 0.647 to 0.778. Confirmatory factor analysis supported a good model fit for the short form ($\chi^2/df = 0.485$; CFI = 1.000; TLI = 1.000; RMSEA = 0.000). Reliability results were satisfactory (Cronbach's alpha = 0.814; composite reliability = 0.807; AVE = 0.458). Overall, the findings provide initial validity and reliability evidence for the Quiet Quitting Scale Short Form in the Turkish context and suggest that it can be used to rapidly assess quiet quitting tendencies in organizational settings.

Keywords: Quiet Quitting, Scale Adaptation, Short-Form Development, Validity, Reliability.

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Research Paper

1. INTRODUCTION

The strategic orientations of businesses, the dynamic environmental conditions in which they operate, their technological competencies, and the nature of the work are accepted as the fundamental elements that shape organizational structure (Chandler, 1969; Mintzberg, 1979). In the classical management literature, in parallel with the formation of these structural elements, the way in which work is performed gains a rational and procedural basis; while task boundaries become clearer for employees, organizational goals become more concrete (Pugh et al., 1968). Within this rational framework, work is defined, at the minimum common denominator, as a set of delimited duties and responsibilities performed in return for a certain wage (Brannick et al., 2007). However, in the modern business world, organizational success and competitive advantage have become tightly dependent not only on employees' adherence to these formal role definitions, but also on their demonstration of "extra effort" by engaging in proactive role expansion and organizational citizenship behaviors (Grant & Parker, 2009). Over time, these extra-role contributions have been assumed to strengthen employees' sense of belonging and have been transformed by organizations from "an exceptional sacrifice" into the status of "a natural expectation." Nevertheless, the radical transformations in working practices triggered particularly by the COVID-19 pandemic, the culture of "being accessible at all times," and the increasing workload have caused employees to develop strong psychological resistance against these implicit expectations (Boy & Sürmeli, 2023; Scheyett, 2022). The phenomenon of "quiet quitting," which has rapidly gained a place in the literature as the most evident reflection of this resistance, is defined as an employee's fulfillment of only the minimum task requirements without having the intention to actually leave the job, and the conscious withdrawal of the voluntary, extra-role contributions provided to the organization (Formica & Sfodera, 2022). Klotz and Bolino (2022) draw attention to the fact that, unlike traditional turnover processes, quiet quitting involves the employee's abandonment of citizenship behaviors such as working overtime, participating in voluntary projects, or taking initiative while continuing to perform core duties at a satisfactory

level. Therefore, an individual who displays quiet quitting behavior does not necessarily exhibit low performance; the basic dynamic here is that the individual draws a "psychological boundary" between work and life in order to protect oneself against burnout (Atiq et al., 2025; Pevec, 2003).

Although the concept has come to the agenda through popular terminology, in essence it has a deep theoretical background based on Social Exchange Theory and breaches of the Psychological Contract. When the literature is examined, quiet quitting is observed to be the result of organizational antecedents such as role ambiguity, organizational injustice, excessive workload, and insufficient supervisor support, as well as employee-related motivational breakdowns such as low job satisfaction, alienation from work, and emotional exhaustion (Hamouche et al., 2023). Patel et al. (2025) emphasize that quiet quitting is not a single act but rather a multidimensional syndrome that includes stages of cognitive and emotional withdrawal. From the perspective of employers, quiet quitting is a "silent crisis" that is much more difficult to measure and detect compared with explicit turnover rates, yet in the long term deeply undermines the organization's innovation capacity and service quality.

While theoretical and empirical efforts to make sense of the antecedents and organizational outcomes of quiet quitting in the global literature (e.g., Galanis et al., 2023; Patel et al., 2025) are rapidly increasing, a significant methodological and conceptual gap is observed in the Turkey-centered local literature in this field. The relevant Turkish literature largely consists of conceptual reviews or narrow evaluations that confine the phenomenon to the traditional context of "turnover intention." In order to empirically test how variables known to be related to quiet quitting, such as burnout, organizational cynicism, work-life balance, and psychological safety, interact in the cultural context of Turkey (especially in work environments where collectivist values and a culture of sacrifice are dominant), there is an urgent need for a quantitative infrastructure that will measure the phenomenon with an internationally standardized and validated instrument.

The aim of this study is to adapt into Turkish the "Quiet Quitting Scale," developed by Talukder and

Prieto (2025), which addresses the phenomenon of quiet quitting not merely as a work-avoidance behavior but within a holistic structure with its cognitive and attitudinal dimensions, and to test evidence of its validity and reliability. The original value that the study offers to the literature is shaped along two axes: first, it provides linguistic integration that enables international and cross-cultural comparative studies by transferring the concept's counterpart in Turkish culture to a quantitative dimension. Second, in order to minimize participant fatigue caused by long scales and to provide researchers with ease of application especially in high-stress field studies (such as in the health, service, and education sectors), it contributes to the literature by presenting the psychometric adequacy of a unidimensional and short measurement instrument that reflects the essence of the concept. In this way, the study aims to present a standard measurement architecture for detecting hidden performance losses and psychological withdrawals in modern workplaces.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1. Ethical Permission

For this study, the necessary ethical permissions were obtained from the Süleyman Demirel University Social and Human Sciences Ethics Committee with the decision dated 17.12.2025 and numbered 182-30.

2.2. Study Group

Within the scope of the study, data were collected from administrative personnel employed at Süleyman Demirel University. Administrative personnel in higher education institutions constitute a relevant sample for examining quiet quitting because they perform essential organizational functions that support academic and institutional processes, yet their work is often less visible than that of academic staff. Previous studies have emphasized that administrative and professional staff in universities represent an important but frequently overlooked workforce whose roles have become increasingly complex, professionalized, and boundary-spanning in contemporary higher education institutions (Szekeres, 2004; Whitchurch, 2008; Gornitzka & Larsen, 2004). Therefore, examining quiet quitting tendencies among university administrative personnel is important for understanding hidden withdrawal behaviors in knowledge-intensive public organizations.

A total of 413 administrative personnel participated in the study. During the data-screening process, 23 questionnaires were excluded because participants marked the attention-check item, which instructed them to leave the item blank. In addition, two multivariate outliers were identified using Mahalanobis distance and removed from the dataset. Thus, the analyses were conducted with data obtained from 388 participants. Of the participants, 242 (62.4%) were women and 146 (37.6%) were men.

2.3. Procedure (Adaptation of the Scale)

In order to adapt the "Quiet Quitting Scale," originally developed by Talukder and Prieto (2025), into Turkish, the scale items were first translated into Turkish by five instructors working at the School of Foreign Languages of Süleyman Demirel University. The translations were reviewed by the researcher, and a draft Turkish form was created. This draft form was then submitted to an expert committee for evaluation.

After the expert review, the Turkish form was translated back into English by faculty members from the Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences. The back-translated form was compared with the original scale items, and minor revisions were made where necessary. After this process, a pilot application was conducted with 35 participants in a classroom setting. Based on the feedback obtained from the pilot application, the final Turkish form was prepared. Thus, linguistic equivalence and clarity of the items were supported in line with the back-translation approach (Brislin, 1970).

2.4. Content Validity

In order to evaluate content validity, the Content Validity Index (CVI) developed by Polit and Beck (2006) was used. Ten academics working as faculty members at the Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences of Süleyman Demirel University were asked to rate the scale items as 1 = not appropriate, 2 = somewhat appropriate, 3 = appropriate, and 4 = definitely appropriate. The scale-level content validity index based on the average method was calculated as 0.98. This finding indicates that the content validity of the scale was supported.

2.5. Measurement Instrument

In this study, the Turkish form of the 10-item Quiet Quitting Scale developed by Talukder and Prieto (2025) was administered to the participants. The

items were rated on a 5-point Likert-type scale in accordance with the original scale (1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neither agree nor disagree, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly agree). The 5-item short form was obtained after the item-reduction analyses conducted within the scope of the present study.

2.6. Data Analysis

In the analyses regarding the Turkish adaptation of the scale, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), and internal consistency reliability analyses were conducted, respectively. The analyses were conducted using SPSS and AMOS. EFA, reliability analyses, descriptive statistics, skewness and kurtosis values were examined in SPSS, while CFA and Mahalanobis distance values were examined in AMOS.

Before proceeding to construct validity procedures, the data were screened for careless responding, missing data, normality, and multivariate outliers. Careless responses were identified through an attention-check item that instructed participants to leave the item blank. Participants who marked this item were excluded from the dataset. Two multivariate outliers were removed based on Mahalanobis distance values in AMOS ($p < .001$). The skewness and kurtosis values of the data were checked, and values between -2 and +2 were accepted as evidence of normal distribution.

Before the short-form analyses, a preliminary EFA was conducted on the original 10-item form using the total sample ($N = 388$). The final dataset consisting of 388 participants was randomly divided into two subsamples; EFA was conducted with the first subsample ($n = 194$), and CFA was conducted with the second subsample ($n = 194$). Then, in order to determine the suitability of the data for factor analysis, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) sampling adequacy analysis and Bartlett's test of sphericity were applied.

During the EFA process, the unidimensional structure of the original scale was evaluated; since the findings indicated that the scale might be suitable for short-form development, an item-reduction approach was followed. EFA was conducted using principal axis factoring. When determining the short-form items, the factor

loadings of the items, the status of the internal consistency reliability value if deleted, the conceptual measurement strength of the items, and their representational ability were evaluated together (Stanton et al., 2002). The unidimensional structure of the short form was tested with CFA, and model fit indices were reported (Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003).

In the reliability analyses, Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability coefficients were calculated; it was taken into account that a Cronbach's alpha value above 0.70 is considered sufficient in the social sciences (George & Mallery, 2019). In addition, average variance extracted (AVE) was calculated to evaluate convergent validity evidence (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

3. RESEARCH FINDINGS

In this section, the validity and reliability findings regarding the Turkish adaptation of the Quiet Quitting Scale are presented. First, EFA and CFA were conducted within the scope of construct validity; then internal consistency reliability and convergent validity evidence were evaluated.

3.1. Construct Validity

Before proceeding to construct validity analyses, the skewness and kurtosis values of the data were examined. In accordance with George and Mallery (2019), values between -2 and +2 were accepted as evidence of normal distribution. In order to determine the suitability of the data for factor analysis, KMO sampling adequacy analysis and Bartlett's test of sphericity were applied; it was determined that the sample was suitable for factor analysis ($KMO = 0.877$; Bartlett $\chi^2(45) = 1601.336$, $p < 0.001$).

As a result of the EFA, a two-factor structure with eigenvalues greater than 1 was obtained. The eigenvalue of the first factor was 4.697, and the eigenvalue of the second factor was 1.087. The first factor explained 46.975% of the total variance, while the second factor explained 10.875%; the cumulative explained variance reached 57.850%. Since the factors were correlated, oblimin rotation was used. The factor correlation was high in magnitude ($r = -0.701$), indicating that the two factors were not independent from each other. Therefore, this result was not interpreted as clear evidence of an independent two-factor structure. Rather, it showed that the original 10-item form required further examination in the Turkish sample.

Table 1. Eigenvalue and Explained Variance Values of the Original 10-Item Form

Factor	Eigenvalue	Explained Variance (%)	Cumulative Variance (%)
Factor 1	4.697	46.975	46.975
Factor 2	1.087	10.875	57.850
N = 388			

Note. Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring; Rotation Method: Oblimin with Kaiser Normalization.

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient of the original 10-item form was calculated as .832. When the eigenvalue and variance distribution presented in Table 1 and the reliability value of the original form are evaluated together, the findings suggested that the item structure of the original form should be examined in more detail for possible short-form development.

Table 2 includes the factor loadings of the items, communality values, and Cronbach's alpha if item deleted values; these indicators were used as preliminary criteria for determining the items to be retained in the short form.

Table 2. Exploratory Factor Analysis Results for the Original 10-Item Quiet Quitting Scale

Item No.	Factor 1	Factor 2	Communality	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
SI1	0.120	-0.468	0.312	0.864
SI2	-0.065	-0.748	0.495	0.860
SI3	0.366	-0.113	0.205	0.872
SI4	0.006	-0.829	0.694	0.851
SI5	0.092	-0.797	0.747	0.848
SI6	0.647	-0.003	0.421	0.861
SI7	0.467	-0.229	0.420	0.858
SI8	0.859	0.123	0.605	0.856
SI9	0.641	-0.143	0.560	0.852
SI10	0.632	0.019	0.383	0.863
N = 388				

Note. Extraction Method: Principal Axis Factoring; Rotation Method: Oblimin with Kaiser Normalization. Values are based on the pattern matrix.

When Table 2, which provides factor loadings and communality values, is examined, it is seen that the original 10-item form produced a two-factor appearance in the Turkish sample. Some items showed relatively low communalities, especially SI3 and SI10, while some items clustered under different factors. In addition, the high correlation between the two factors indicated that the factors were not independent from each other. In light of all this information, it was decided to examine the existing structure in the scale together with its reasons.

In this context, the options of accepting the two-factor structure as it is for the Turkish adaptation of the scale, forcing a one-factor structure by keeping the number of questions the same or by excluding low-factor items from the analysis, making changes to the scale items or structure, and examining item discriminations through Rasch Analysis were evaluated. As a result of the analyses

and examinations carried out, it was determined that the Quiet Quitting Scale, which originally consists of 10 items and one dimension, could be evaluated for short-form development without making any changes to the original item statements.

The main reasons for this decision were reducing the application time, increasing measurement efficiency by measuring the same structure with fewer items, strengthening the unidimensional structure, ensuring organizational consistency, and facilitating its applicability in multivariate models. Indeed, as the number of items in a scale increases, it may cause fatigue among participants and increase measurement error (Burisch, 1984). In addition, Smith et al. (2000) stated that short forms should be preferred if similar psychometric results can be obtained with fewer items. Similarly, the possibility that some items may lose their function in cultural scale adaptations (Van de

Vijver & Leung, 1997) requires scales to be evaluated also in terms of the number of items during adaptation.

When determining the items suitable for the short form, the factor loadings of the items, communality values, internal consistency reliability values, conceptual measurement strength, and representational ability were evaluated together (Stanton et al., 2002). Indeed, it is accepted that items that distribute meaningfully across more than one factor may

weaken measurement power (Costello & Osborne, 2005). In addition, the presence of conceptually similar items reduces the efficiency of the scale (Burisch, 1984). Likewise, when evaluating the items in the scale, evaluating only statistical results remains insufficient; the items are expected to be adequate in terms of representing the concept being measured (Hinkin, 1998). In line with these criteria, SI4, SI6, SI7, SI8, and SI9 were retained in the short form. Table 3 presents the item selections and their justifications for the scale items.

Table 3. Selection and Elimination Justifications for the Items

Item No.	Decision	Factor Loading (F1/F2)	Communality	Statistical Justification	Conceptual Justification	Literature
1	Eliminated	0.120 / -0.468	0.312	Lower contribution to the final short-form structure	Less direct representation of the core behavioral withdrawal pattern	Hinkin (1998)
2	Eliminated	-0.065 / -0.748	0.495	Not retained in the final short-form model	Conceptual overlap with minimum-effort items	Smith et al. (2000)
3	Eliminated	0.366 / -0.113	0.205	Low communality	Not directly focused on role-based quiet quitting behavior	Hinkin (1998)
4	Retained	0.006 / -0.829	0.694	High factor loading and strong communality	Direct measurement of minimum required work behavior	Hinkin (1998)
5	Eliminated	0.092 / -0.797	0.747	Not retained due to content overlap in the short-form structure	Conceptual overlap with minimum-effort and compensation-related items	Stanton et al. (2002)
6	Retained	0.647 / -0.003	0.421	Acceptable factor loading in the final short-form structure	Work-life boundary and refusal of extra-role availability	Costello & Osborne (2005)
7	Retained	0.467 / -0.229	0.420	Acceptable factor loading and conceptual contribution	Avoidance of others' projects and extra-role work	Hinkin (1998)
8	Retained	0.859 / 0.123	0.605	High factor loading and adequate communality	Resistance to giving all effort or working extra hours	Stanton et al. (2002)
9	Retained	0.641 / -0.143	0.560	High factor loading and adequate communality	Direct representation of not going the extra mile	Smith et al. (2000)
10	Eliminated	0.632 / 0.019	0.383	Lower communality compared with retained items	Less central to the core short-form structure	Worthington & Whittaker (2006)

Note. Factor loadings are based on the pattern matrix obtained through principal axis factoring with oblimin rotation.

As seen in Table 3, the 10-item original form was reduced to a short form consisting of 5 items: SI4, SI6, SI7, SI8, and SI9. During the selection of these items, the criteria determined by Hinkin (1998), Smith et al. (2000), Stanton et al. (2002), and Worthington and Whittaker (2006) were followed. In this process, the factor structure, factor loadings, communalities, internal consistency analyses, construct purity, redundancy control for the short form, and preservation of scope were examined.

Although the statistical indicators guided the item selection process, the scope of the items and their suitability for the core concept were also evaluated by comparison with the relevant literature. In this context, the items in the scale

were examined one by one together with factor loadings, communality, and internal reliability coefficients. While the analyses were conducted, importance was attached to distinguishing the concept from constructs such as turnover intention, burnout, and work-life balance.

In addition, items expressing role-based behaviors such as adherence to the role definition, avoidance of extra effort, refusal of extra-role availability, and withdrawal from organizational citizenship were identified in accordance with the core definition of quiet quitting. After these procedures, the testing phase of the 5-item short form was initiated. In this context, exploratory factor analysis, confirmatory factor analysis, and internal consistency reliability analyses were conducted, respectively.

3.2. Construct Validity of the Short Form

In order to determine the suitability of the short-form data for factor analysis, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin sampling adequacy analysis and Bartlett's test of sphericity were conducted in the EFA subsample. As a result of these analyses, it was concluded that the sample was adequate and suitable for factor analysis (KMO = 0.822, Bartlett $\chi^2(10) = 320.146$, $p < 0.001$). As a result of the exploratory factor analysis, it was determined that the factor loadings of the items ranged between 0.647 and

0.778, while the communality values ranged between 0.419 and 0.606.

In addition, a one-factor structure with an eigenvalue greater than 1 was obtained. The eigenvalue of this factor was 2.934. Based on the initial eigenvalues, it explained 58.685% of the total variance. After principal axis factoring extraction, the explained variance was 48.619%. In light of this information, confirmatory factor analysis was initiated in the CFA subsample.

Figure 1. First-Order CFA Results of the Quiet Quitting Scale Short Form

As shown in Figure 1, the factor loadings of the items belonging to the Quiet Quitting Scale Short Form were within acceptable ranges. In addition, when the goodness-of-fit values are examined ($\chi^2(5) = 2.427$, $p = 0.787$; $\chi^2/df = 0.485$; CFI = 1.000; NFI = 0.991; IFI = 1.009; TLI = 1.000; GFI = 0.995; AGFI = 0.985; RMSEA = 0.000; RMR = 0.024), it can be stated that the model fit was supported. Since IFI and TLI values may exceed 1.00 in some model estimations, these values were interpreted as indicating excellent fit.

Since the short form items are a subset of the original scale, the relationship between the short form and the original form was not interpreted as independent validity evidence. Therefore, the validity evidence of the short form was evaluated through the EFA and CFA results, composite reliability, AVE, and internal consistency findings.

3.3. Reliability Findings

In order to determine the reliability values of the Quiet Quitting Scale Short Form, internal reliability coefficients were examined. The reliability coefficients and item statistics for the form are given in detail in Table 4.

Table 4. Item Analysis Results of the Quiet Quitting Scale Short Form

Item No.	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
SI4	0.579	0.797
SI6	0.576	0.799
SI7	0.579	0.798
SI8	0.664	0.773
SI9	0.684	0.767

Note. N = 194. Cronbach's alpha = .822.

According to the item analysis results in Table 4, all of the items have corrected item-total correlations ranging from 0.576 to 0.684. These results show

that the items adequately and consistently represent the short-form structure. Indeed, DeVellis and Thorpe (2021) stated that item correlations above 0.30 can be considered acceptable and that item correlations of 0.40 and above have strong item discrimination.

In the reliability analyses conducted, Cronbach's α was determined as 0.832 for the original 10-item form, 0.822 for the short form in the EFA subsample, and 0.814 for the short form in the total sample. A Cronbach's α value above 0.70 is considered sufficient for the social sciences (George & Mallery, 2019). In addition, composite reliability was calculated as 0.807, while AVE was calculated as 0.458. Although the AVE value was

slightly below the conventional 0.50 threshold, the composite reliability value was above 0.70 and the standardized factor loadings were acceptable. Therefore, the convergent validity evidence of the short form was considered acceptable, but this evidence should be retested in future studies with different samples.

3.4. Turkish Item Statements of the Short Form

The Turkish item statements of the final short form consisting of SI4, SI6, SI7, SI8, and SI9 are presented in Table 5. The items in the scale are rated on a 5-point Likert type scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). In the application of the short form, an increase in the total score indicates an increase in quiet quitting tendency.

Table 5. Turkish Item Statements of the Quiet Quitting Scale Short Form

Item No.	Statements
1	İşe gelir ve yalnızca benden beklenen asgari işleri yaparım; bunun çok ötesine geçmem.
2	Daha sık "hayır" demeyi, akşamlarımı kendime ayırmayı ve tatildeyken e-postalarımı kontrol etmemeyi öğrendim.
3	Başkalarına ait projelerde yer almaktan kaçınırım.
4	İşime tüm enerjimi verme ya da fazla mesai yapma beklentisine direnirim.
5	İş yerinde görev tanımımın ötesine geçmemeyi tercih ederim.

4. CONCLUSION

This study focused on adapting the Quiet Quitting Scale developed by Talukder and Prieto (2025) into Turkish and revealing the psychometric properties of the scale's short form. The analyses conducted with data obtained from 388 administrative personnel employed at Süleyman Demirel University showed that the tendency toward quiet quitting can be measured meaningfully and consistently in the Turkish context through a unidimensional short structure. The construct validity findings of the short form supported the one-factor structure; the factor loadings of the items were in the range of 0.647–0.778 in the EFA subsample. This structure was also confirmed by CFA, and the fit indices were found to be at a good level ($\chi^2(5) = 2.427$, $p = 0.787$; $\chi^2/df = 0.485$; CFI = 1.000; TLI = 1.000; RMSEA = 0.000). Reliability analyses showed that the internal consistency of the short form was satisfactory (Cronbach's alpha

= 0.814). In addition, composite reliability was 0.807 and AVE was 0.458. Although the AVE value was slightly below the conventional threshold, the factor loadings and composite reliability value supported the convergent validity evidence of the short form.

These findings make the theoretical and practical contributions of the study more visible. From a theoretical perspective, the study goes beyond popular interpretations that equate quiet quitting with "turnover intention" or "low performance" and strengthens the measurability of the core withdrawal pattern in the Turkish context, which is manifested as limiting voluntary extra effort and organizational citizenship behaviors while maintaining role requirements. The EFA and CFA evidence presented for the unidimensional structure supports the idea that the concept can be addressed within a holistic framework; thus, it provides a measurement basis for more consistently discussing the boundaries of quiet

quitting with related concepts such as burnout, organizational cynicism, and turnover intention.

From a practical perspective, because quiet quitting is a form of withdrawal that often progresses “invisibly” in organizations, it is important to measure it reliably and rapidly. Through the 5-item short form, this study makes it possible to monitor quiet quitting with a measurement that imposes low time and respondent burden. The applicability of the short form may contribute not only to facilitating data collection in field research, but also to producing early-warning findings in human resources practices such as monitoring employee engagement and well-being, and evaluations before or after intervention programs. In this way, quiet quitting can be addressed not only as a current discourse but also as a measurable phenomenon that can support evidence-based management processes.

Nevertheless, the findings should be evaluated within the framework of some limitations. The limitation of the sample to administrative personnel working at a single public university may restrict the direct generalization of the results to different sectors, regions, and occupational groups. In addition, the fact that the data are based on self-report may raise the possibility of common method variance. Another limitation is that the present study did not test the relationships of the short form with external criterion variables such as job satisfaction, burnout, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, or turnover intention. In addition, the AVE value was slightly below the conventional 0.50 threshold. Although this result was evaluated together with the acceptable factor loadings and composite reliability value, future studies should retest the convergent validity evidence of the short form in different samples. In future research, confirming the scale in different samples, testing its relationships with external criterion variables, examining its stability over time, and evaluating measurement invariance across different subgroups will further support the evidence base of the scale.

Overall, the results obtained provide initial evidence that the Quiet Quitting Scale Short Form

is a valid, reliable, and practical measurement instrument in the Turkish context. However, further studies are needed to test the short form in different samples, sectors, and organizational contexts.

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